

COMPOSITE TUBE POST-CURE SHRINKAGE INCLUDING SHEAR EFFECTS

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SUMMARY: A model is presented which allows the thermal analysis of finite length, orthotropic tubes. A numerical heat transfer model is implemented which allows the temperature variation through the thickness of the tube to be determined as a function of time. The displacement based Rayleigh-Ritz technique is utilised to determine the stress/strain state of the tube under a temperature gradient. Provision is made to allow two dimensional variation in the displacement functions and thus, allowance is made for the effects of the shear strain. The model is therefore able to account for a tube of finite length. The present model is validated against existing results. Results are shown for a tube constructed of chopped strand mat subject to a fixed temperature at the inner wall and free convection on the outer wall. It is shown that the effect of shear strain on the stress behaviour of the tube is significant.

KEYWORDS: Residual stress, thick-walled vessels, Rayleigh-Ritz, thermal stress

INTRODUCTION

Thermal expansion of a homogeneous flat plate will result in a null stress state. This is due to the fact that, barring any applied edge constraint, the expansions in the plate will be unrestrained. In the case of a curved structure manufactured from a material having different coefficients of thermal expansion in the through-thickness and in-plane directions, thermal loading will result in superimposed curvature. If the curvature is resisted, a state of stress will result. Consequently, an orthotropic cylinder under thermal loading will be subject to a non-zero stress state [1,2].

In thin-walled analyses, these stresses can be ignored because the induced change in curvature is negligible. However, as the wall thickness to diameter ratio increases, these stresses become significant and must be accounted for [1,2]. In the case of the post-cure of composite tubes, these stresses manifest themselves as residual stresses due to the thermal loading during the post-cure operation. These residual stresses have an adverse effect on the ability of the vessel to resist environmentally assisted cracking (EAC) and corrosion, and can cause failure well before the design stress [1].

Whilst it is possible to predict the stresses using an FEM analysis, the time spent building, running and validating such models can be significant. This is especially the case if this analysis occurs during the design phase of the vessel, since it can be expected that the configuration of the vessel will undergo many modifications. The Rayleigh-Ritz technique shares similarities with FEM in that they are both approximate energy based techniques. However, as the Rayleigh-Ritz technique can be directly formulated for a particular geometry,

the Degrees-of-Freedom (DOF's) and run time can be less than that required for a general FEM analysis.

Stone *et al* [1] utilised the Rayleigh-Ritz technique to predict the residual stresses due to post-cure on composite tubes. This work allows the accurate prediction of the residual stresses far away from the ends in a long tube. As this axisymmetric model only allows for strain variation through the radius of the tube but not along the length, it is unable to predict the stresses along the length of the tube, including the stresses at the end.

Kardomateas [2] presented an analytical model for the transient thermal stresses in a homogeneous orthotropic tube. In a similar manner to Stone *et al* [1], axial displacement is allowed a linear variation. Thus the stress state predicted is that for a long tube away from the ends. In the current work provision is made to allow for a non-constant temperature distribution with the tube radius. It is thus capable of describing the transient deformation and stress behaviour of the tube resulting from time-varying temperature distribution. In the analysis of the transient problem it was shown by Kardomateas [2] that the stresses during the transient process may in fact be of greater magnitude than those of the steady state.

The present work extends the works of Stone *et al* [1] and Kardomateas [2] to include the shear strain term, γ_{rz} and to allow for 2 dimensional variation in each of the independent displacements. The current model is therefore based on a fully 3-D axisymmetric analysis. The implication of this extension is that it is now possible to model the variation in the stress state both along the radial and the axial co-ordinates. A numerical model is implemented to allow the heat transfer problem to be solved for. The stress model is modified so as to account for a temperature variation through the thickness of the tube. By virtue of these extensions, it is now possible to accurately model an orthotropic cylinder of finite length.

PROBLEM FORMULATION

Formulation of Heat Transfer Model

In this work, an explicit first order differencing method was implemented to analyse the heat transfer problem of the tube [3]. It was assumed that the heat loss through the ends would be negligible and therefore the temperature of the tube would only vary through the thickness. As is typical in numerical methods, the thickness of the tube is divided into a number of regions. By considering the ability of each region to store internal thermal energy as well as its ability to transfer the energy to the neighbouring regions by conduction, it is possible to determine the thermal gradient throughout the thickness at any time. The node on the outer wall transfers heat by means of convection to the surroundings.

The solution is an explicit, marching solution, thus the new region temperature is calculated from the values obtained during the previous time step. In this way, there is no iteration in the solution; however, the maximum permissible time step is a function of the discretised region size. This indicates that the solution accuracy is determined only by the size of the nodal spacing and not by the time step. Once the time step exceeds this value the errors between time steps are amplified and propagated and the solution quickly becomes unstable [3].

The nodal temperatures at the $(i+1)^{th}$ time step are calculated as:

$$T_m^{i+1} = T_m^i \left(1 - \frac{2K\Delta t}{\Delta r^2} \right) + \frac{K\Delta t}{r_m \Delta r^2} \left[T_{m-1}^i \left(r_m - \frac{\Delta r}{2} \right) + T_{m+1}^i \left(r_m + \frac{\Delta r}{2} \right) \right] \quad (1)$$

$$T_m^{i+1} = T_m^i \left[1 - \frac{2K\Delta t}{\Delta r^2} \left(r_m - \frac{\Delta r}{2} \right) - \frac{2\Delta t h}{\Delta r} \right] + \frac{2K\Delta t T_{m-1}^i (r_m - \Delta r/2)}{r_m \Delta r^2} + \frac{2h\Delta t}{\Delta r} T_e \quad (2)$$

where T_m^i is the temperature of the m^{th} node in degrees Celcius at time i , [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]; K is the material thermal diffusivity in the radial direction, [m^2/s]; h is the ratio between the convective heat transfer coefficient and the conductive heat transfer co-efficient for the material, [m^{-1}].

Due to the nature of the simulation, the conduction and convection boundary conditions both enforce stability constraints on the simulation. The relationships governing these conditions are given by

$$\Delta t_{\max} = \frac{\Delta r^2}{K} \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta t_{\max} = \frac{r_o \Delta r^2}{2[(r_o - \Delta r/2)K + hr_o \Delta r]} \quad (4)$$

where r_o is the outer wall radius [3]. The minimum value of Δt_{\max} then becomes the maximum permissible time step.

It should also be noted that temperature independent material properties were assumed in this work. As this work considers homogenous tubes with no internal heat generation, it is expected that the temperature gradient calculated by this model will vary smoothly. It should thus be possible to accurately approximate the gradient by using the least-squares method to obtain a polynomial of a chosen order. This polynomial can then be incorporated into the stress/strain model.

Formulation of Stress/Strain Model

Due to the nature of the geometry of the problem, the cylindrical reference frame would be the most appropriate for the analysis. As the geometry, loading and material properties utilized in this work are symmetric about the axis of rotation of the tube it is possible to assume the problem to be an axisymmetric one. Thus, the shear strains $\gamma_{z\theta}$ and $\gamma_{r\theta}$ will be zero. Additionally, the displacements (u_z , u_r , and u_θ) will be independent of the angular co-ordinate, θ . There are thus only two independent displacements, the axial and radial displacements, (u_z , u_r).

In order to perform the Rayleigh-Ritz analysis, the independent displacements are written as general polynomial expansions of the co-ordinates z , r as:

$$u_z = \sum_{m=0}^M \sum_{n=0}^N W_{mn} z^m r^n, \quad u_r = \sum_{p=0}^P \sum_{q=0}^Q W_{pq} r^p z^q \quad (5)$$

For purposes of analysis, it is convenient to rewrite Eqn. 5 in terms of generalized dimensionless co-ordinates for both the axial and radial co-ordinates. Eqn. 5 therefore becomes:

$$u_z = \sum_{m=0}^M \sum_{n=0}^N W_{mn} Z^m R^n, \quad u_r = \sum_{p=0}^P \sum_{q=0}^Q W_{pq} R^p Z^q \quad (6)$$

where:

$$Z = \frac{z}{L}; \quad R = \frac{r - r_i}{t} \quad (7)$$

In the above L is the length, t is the thickness and r_i is the internal radius of the tube. The array of W_{ij} is the vector of displacement coefficients.

As the order of the series in Eqn. 6 increases, so does the descriptive ability of the Rayleigh-Ritz solution to capture the displacement behaviour in the problem. However, if the order of the polynomials is increased indefinitely, numerical instability will occur. Thus the Rayleigh-Ritz technique is highly capable of describing problems in which the displacements are smooth and do not exhibit sudden variation. As the displacements vary considerably along the length of the tube (particularly in a localised region near the free end), it was necessary to discretize the tube along its length. This allows the displacements in the localised region near the free end to be adequately described.

The constitutive equations for the tube are given by:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{zz} \\ \sigma_{\theta\theta} \\ \sigma_{rr} \\ \tau_{zr} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & 0 \\ C_{12} & C_{22} & C_{23} & 0 \\ C_{31} & C_{32} & C_{33} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{zz} - \alpha_{zz}\Delta T \\ \varepsilon_{\theta\theta} - \alpha_{\theta\theta}\Delta T \\ \varepsilon_{rr} - \alpha_{rr}\Delta T \\ \gamma_{zr} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

where the matrix C forms the standard compliance matrix for an orthotropic material. ΔT is the change in temperature from the stress-free reference temperature. As the temperature varies through the thickness in this analysis, ΔT will be dependent on the co-ordinate R according to the results from the heat transfer model.

The Rayleigh-Ritz solution involves minimizing the total potential energy of the tube which is given by:

$$\Pi = \frac{1}{2} \iiint_V \varepsilon^T C \varepsilon dV \quad (9)$$

By minimizing the potential energy, it is possible to write the problem in the form:

$$K W = L \quad (10)$$

where K is the stiffness matrix of the tube and L the loading matrix.

Equation 10 can be solved by conventional methods, such as Gaussian elimination, to obtain the displacement coefficients.

As is typical in analyses of this form, each of the discretised regions possesses a local stiffness and loading matrix which are combined to form the global matrix problem in Eqn. 10. Additionally, symmetry boundary conditions were applied at the middle of the tube and compatibility was enforced between the discretised regions. By fitting a least squares

polynomial to the temperature variation, it becomes possible to write the thermal strains as a polynomial in terms of R . Thus the integrations required for Eqn. 10 can be performed with ease.

RESULTS

Model Validation

The validation of the heat transfer model was accomplished by comparing the results to the existing analytical results [2]. In this work the problem consists of a tube which is subject to a known, constant temperature of 100 °C at the inner wall and allowed to dissipate heat by convection at the outer wall. The comparison of results is presented in Fig. 1. In the numerical simulation, 1000 nodes were used across the thickness of the tube and the resulting time step was chosen as 1.14×10^{-4} s by virtue of Eqn.'s 3 and 4. In order to compare the results the non-dimensional time was calculated as:

$$\bar{t} = \frac{tK}{(r_o - r_i)^2} \quad (11)$$

Fig. 1 – Comparison of the Temperature Distribution Through the Thickness of an Orthotropic Tube

As can be seen, excellent agreement is found between the solutions. With the solution parameters chosen in this analysis it was found that a fairly high degree of accuracy was attained (<1%) while the solution time was not extensive (in the order of 10 min on a desktop computer).

The heat transfer results were applied in the calculation of the stresses for the tube. As the analytical work applies only for a long tube, it is necessary to present the results at the middle of the tube since the shear stress is zero at this point. The Rayleigh-Ritz solution was compared to the results obtained from FEM in Fig.'s 2-5. The Rayleigh-Ritz solution showed excellent agreement with the FEM results at all time steps. However, these results did not agree with those presented by Kardomateas [2].

Fig. 2 – Stress Variation Through the Thickness ($\bar{t} = 0.25$)

Fig. 3 – Stress Variation Through the Thickness ($\bar{t} = 0.5$)

Fig. 4 – Stress Variation Through the Thickness ($\bar{t} = 1.0$)

Fig. 5 – Stress Variation Through the Thickness ($\bar{t} = 10$)

Results for a Finite Length Orthotropic Tube

For the purposes of this work, the behaviour of an open tube was investigated. The tube had an inner radius of 250 mm and a wall thickness of 100 mm. The length of the tube was 2000 mm. The tube was constructed of chopped strand mat (CSM) the properties of which were determined from test data and by application of the rule of mixtures, listed in Table 1 [4]. The tube was subject to a constant temperature of 150 °C at the inner wall. The free convection of the tube to air was simulated with a convection heat transfer co-efficient of 10 W/m²K.

Table 1: Material Properties for Chopped Strand Mat

Material Property	Magnitude
E_1	9670 MPa
E_2	9670 MPa
E_3	6320 MPa
G_{12}	4120 MPa
ν_{12}	0.340
ν_{13}	0.390
ν_{23}	0.390
α_z	-26.79×10^{-6}
α_θ	-26.79×10^{-6}
α_r	-78.42×10^{-6}
K	$1.128 \times 10^{-7} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$

The heat transfer was simulated with 100 nodes through the thickness. It was found that the tube attained a steady-state temperature distribution after approximately 70 hours. The final steady-state temperature distribution is presented in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6 – Steady-State Temperature Variation of the CSM Tube

A fifth order least squares curve was fitted to the temperature distribution in Fig. 6 for the purposes of the stress analysis. For the analysis of this tube, displacement functions with orders of: $N = M = Q = 6$, $P = 9$ describe the displacements sufficiently. Additionally the tube was discretised into 4 regions along the length. The length of each of the regions was determined from a geometric series such that:

$$\frac{L_{n+1}}{L_n} = \frac{1}{2} \quad (12)$$

This enables the regions to become shorter near the end of the tube thus improving the descriptive capability in the area where there are large changes in displacements. Fig.'s 7 and 8 show the stresses at the middle ($z = 0$) and at the free end of the tube respectively. Fig. 9 shows the variation in stress along the length at the midpoint of the thickness.

Fig. 7 – Stress Variation Through the Thickness, (Middle of the Tube)

Fig. 8 – Stress Variation Through the Thickness, (Free End)

Fig. 9 – Stress Variation Along the Length, ($R = 0.5$)

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The model validation showed that the present model agreed with the heat transfer results of Kardomateas as well as the stress results of the FEM. From the results presented it can be seen that the model does satisfy the required equilibrium conditions. The radial and shear stress are zero at the inner and outer walls, and the axial and shear stresses are zero at the free end as shown in Fig. 8.

The stress results on the centreline would closely resemble the results obtained by neglecting the shear effects (bearing in mind that in previous work the axial displacement was only allowed a linear variation whereas in this work the axial displacement is allowed high order variation [1]). However, as can be seen in Fig. 9, there is a notable change in stresses along the length. In particular, the hoop stress on the midpoint of the thickness is seen to undergo a large variation along the length. Therefore the presence of the shear stress impresses a significant variation on the other stress components. The large variation in stress indicates the

significance of considering the finite length tube as opposed to the infinite case. The effects near the ends can differ appreciably from the behaviour near the middle of the tube.

It is worth noting that the FEM is only capable of applying temperature variation at discrete nodal points. Thus, a fairly fine mesh is required to accurately simulate the smooth temperature variation. In contrast, the Rayleigh-Ritz model presented accounts for the smooth temperature variation exactly through the thickness (within the limits of accuracy of the chosen polynomial fit).

CONCLUSIONS

By incorporating the effect of the through-thickness shear strain, existing work on the thermal and stress analysis of 2-D axisymmetric orthotropic long tubes was extended to allow for the analysis of a finite length orthotropic tube. A numerical heat transfer model was implemented which allowed the determination of the temperature variation through the thickness of the tube with time. It is thus possible to determine the complete state of time-varying thermal residual stresses in the tube. This work therefore enables analysis of cure-shrinkage and corresponding stresses, including through-thickness shear stress as a function of time and temperature.

The model was validated against the existing results as well as those obtained from a commercial FEM software package. Investigation of the results obtained from the model indicates that the model satisfies the required equilibrium conditions for the analysis of a free, open ended tube under thermal expansion.

REFERENCES

1. Stone, M.A., Schwartz, I.F. and Chandler, H.D., "Residual Stresses Associated with Post-cure Shrinkage in GRP Tubes", *Composite Science and Technology*, **57**, 1997, pp. 47-54.
2. Kardomateas, G.A., "Transient Thermal Stresses in Cylindrically Orthotropic Tubes", *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, **56**, 1989, pp. 411-417.
3. Mills, A.F., *Heat Transfer – Second Edition*, Prentice Hall Inc, Upper Saddle River, New Jersey, 1999.
4. Whitfield, G.S., *Investigation of the Fabrication and Post-Cure Strains and Spring Back in Glass Fibre Reinforced Pipe Flanges*, MSc Dissertation, University of the Witwatersrand, 2003